

DELIVERABLE

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D2.2 Profile of training opportunities

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0.2	14/11/11	K Snow	HATII	Revised draft with analysis of registry data
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Statement of originality:

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the work carried out by DigCurV Work Package 2 for the profile of training opportunities.

Section 2 outlines Work Package 2 and how the profiling activity relates to the work package as a whole.

Section 3 describes the methodology used for gathering data to feed into the profiling work.

Section 4 discusses the design of the profile registry, the headings used to describe current digital curation courses and the final look of the webpages.

Finally, **Section 5** considers future use of the registry and how the project can ensure its development by the cultural heritage community.

This report accompanies the main output of the profiling activity, which is a training opportunities registry available at: <http://www.digcur-education.org/eng/Training-opportunities>.

2. Introduction

DigCurV aims to support and extend vocational education and training in digital curation for existing professionals by establishing a curriculum framework and building a stakeholder network including organisations involved in this field. The project is analysing existing approaches, methodologies and expertise to inform the development of the curriculum. The results will be disseminated in the appropriate circles across Europe and internationally to improve the quality, visibility, and transparency of continuing vocational training for curators working in the cultural sector.

2.1 Outline of Work Package 2

Work Package 2 is the 'Review of existing training initiatives, resources and methodologies'. The overall aim of this work package is to identify and analyse current training activities in the field of digital curation which, together with the review of sector training needs being carried out in Work Package 3, will inform the subsequent design of the DigCurV curriculum. The specific aim of the profiling activity (described in this document) is to contribute to the development of the core curriculum which will be designed to offer practitioners with a framework for continuous professional development in digital curation, addressing the skills and competencies identified in Work Package 3 and the best practices and innovation identified during these early stages of DigCurV.

The work package consists of three phases of activity:

1. The production and analysis of a **survey of training opportunities**, to find out more about existing training courses in digital curation;
2. The establishment of a structured information base that **profiles training opportunities** in digital curation that are currently available, populated with entries gained from the survey results and further desk research;
3. The development of an **evaluation framework** for the DigCurV training curriculum, based on analysis of the results from the first two activities and the results of Work Package 3.

This report describes the work carried out for the second activity, the profile of training opportunities. The results of the work for phases one and three will be discussed fully in the forthcoming D2.1 'Report on baseline survey and evaluation framework', led by Vilnius University Library (VUL).

3. Training profile methodology

The aim of the training profiling work is twofold; firstly, to build an information base or registry of current digital curation training opportunities, and secondly, to allow for subsequent analysis of the data collected for the registry to identify skills, levels and competencies that will form the evaluation framework. The work package therefore began by collecting the data that would be necessary for the registry and analysis, and approached this by conducting a survey and carrying out desk research.

3.1 Survey of training opportunities

As outlined in the Description of Work, a significant amount of the data for the DigCurV registry was to be taken from the results of a survey of training opportunities, which was designed and conducted by Vilnius University Library (VUL) in April 2011. This asked basic details about events delivered but also more in-depth information on teaching methods, learning objectives, audiences and assessment/accreditation. A more detailed description of the survey and analysis of its results will be provided in D2.1.

The information that respondents provided, covering approximately fifty courses, was then gathered for entry into the registry.

3.2 Desk research

Alongside data gleaned from the survey, the work package also conducted desk research into existing training courses and initiatives that had not been covered in the responses. The approach to inclusion in the registry was as follows:

- that the course was findable online;
- that it related to training in some aspect of the digital curation lifecycle;
- that there was enough information about the course available to produce a useful entry for the registry;
- that it was either post-first degree level or aimed at practitioners already working in the field (i.e. not undergraduate module or equivalent).

This activity gathered details on a further sixteen courses that could be fed into the registry.

4. Design of the DigCurV registry

Once the work package had gathered a useful body of data it then considered the best way to design an information base or registry. The aim was to display the information in 'an accessible and clearly segmented format through the project web site in a way that enables moderated contributions in future'. The work package agreed that the best way to meet this requirement would be through a web-based registry accessible from the DigCurV website. This would enable cultural heritage institutions and digital curation competence centres easy access to the data and also to add new entries, and in this way build the resource into a valuable reference for the digital curation community. Work was then begun by HATII and MDR on designing a registry that would best meet these needs.

4.1 Consideration of existing resources

A number of existing registries and databases related to digital curation training have been produced by other projects and initiatives and these were consulted prior to designing the DigCurV training profile registry. HATII considered how other relevant resources describe and sort training events, including those which deliberately present them as 'registries' or similar, as well as those with a more informal layout such as an 'Events' page. The resources looked at include registries and webpages by DPE¹, Planets², DPOE³, DCC⁴, DPC⁵, Digital Curation Exchange⁶ and JISC⁷. This consultation allowed a list of headings to be drawn up that were widely used and appeared most relevant for describing digital curation training.

Consideration was also given to the DPOE pyramid⁸, which outlines the audience types it is necessary to engage with in order to establish successful digital preservation programmes, and the learning requirements for each. As part of the profiling work and planning for the registry the DPOE headings were reviewed and it was decided to use these as a way of

¹ DPE Registries <http://www.digitalpreservationeurope.eu/registries/>

² Planets Events <http://www.planets-project.eu/events/>

³ DPOE events page <http://www.digitalpreservation.gov/news/events/index.html>

⁴ DCC Events <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/events>

⁵ DPC Events <http://www.dpconline.org/events>

⁶ Digital Curation Exchange Events http://digitalcurationexchange.org/?q=calendar/event_list

⁷ JISC Events <http://www.jisc.ac.uk/events.aspx>

⁸ DPOE pyramid <http://www.digitalpreservation.gov/education/index.html>

refining audience type in the DigCurV registry. The DPOE pyramid will also inform the basis for the evaluation framework, which will be reported in D2.1.

4.2 Arrangement of headings

The research described above allowed a definitive list of headings to be drawn up for the training profile registry. They are as follows:

Overview page

- Organisation
- Title of the course
- Country
- Date(s)
- Language
- Contact person / contact e-mail

Details page (in addition to overview headings)

- Location
- Learning objectives
- Target audience – (options of ‘executive’; ‘managerial’; ‘practical’)
- Training fee
- Website
- Description

It was decided to split entries over two levels to make them easier to read in an online environment. A decision was also taken to keep the date field optional and open, after initial data entry flagged that some repeated courses have varying dates, and that online courses usually have no start or end dates. An optional field for this category allows for more accurate recording of a variety of relevant courses.

The online forms for the registry were designed and implemented by MDR.

4.3 Location and access to registry

HATII and VUL populated the registry with the data accrued in the survey and by desk research, and the registry was made available in the public area of the DigCurV website. The registry can be accessed at the following address:

<http://www.digcur-education.org/eng/Training-opportunities>

Below are examples of the overview page and a full entry from the registry.

Training opportunities / Home page - DigCurV

Site map Register Login Eng Ger Ita Ltu

About Join Us News Events **Training opportunities** Resources Links

Home page > Training opportunities

Training opportunities

DigCurV is compiling information about training opportunities.

If you have details of a course or workshop that you would like included, please contact courses@digcur-education.org.

Show 25 entries Search:

Start Date (Duration)	Organisation	Course	Country	Language
10/11/2010 (21 months)	Stuttgart State Academy of Art and Design	Digital Curation (part of master's program called Preservation of New Media and Digital Information)	Germany	English German
14/11/2011 (3 days)	University of London Computer Centre	Digital Preservation Training Programme	United Kingdom	English
16/11/2011 (6 hours)	JISC	Introduction to Image Metadata	United Kingdom	English
17/11/2011 (6 hours)	British Library	Writing and Using a Preservation Policy	United Kingdom	English
21/11/2011 (6 hours)	JISC Digital Media	BTEC Professional Certificate in Digital Imaging	United Kingdom	English
21/11/2011 (4 hours)	nestor/DigCurV	nestor/DigCurV Winter School 2011: "Langzeitarchivierung in der Praxis"	Germany	German

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Figure 1: Overview page of DigCurV training opportunities registry

Digital Preservation Training Programme / Traini...

Site map Register Login Eng Ger Ita Ltu

About Join Us News Events **Training opportunities** Resources Links

Home page > Training opportunities > Digital Preservation Training Programme

Digital Preservation Training Programme

Organisation University of London Computer Centre

Location School of Oriental and African Studies, London

Country United Kingdom

Language English

Learning Objectives Menu of course modules each with learning objectives available at <http://www.dptp.org/course/>.

Training Fee GBP 650 + VAT

Target Audience Practical

Website <http://www.dptp.org/>

Contact E-Mail <http://www.dptp.org/contact/>

Date 14 Nov 2011 - 16 Nov 11

The Digital Preservation Training Programme (DPTP) is designed for all those working in institutional information management who are grappling with fundamental issues of digital preservation. It provides the skills and knowledge necessary for institutions to combine organisational and technological perspectives, and devise an appropriate response to the challenges that digital preservation needs present. DPTP is operated and organised by the University of London Computer Centre (ULCC), with contributions from leading experts in the field. "DPTP: a veritable Swiss army knife of tools, models, maps, trends and critical thinking. If you are venturing into the world of digital preservation, do not leave home without it." (Sandy Ryan, British Library)

1. Based on [DPOE audience levels](#).

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Figure 2: Detailed entry from DigCurV training opportunities registry

5. Observations and analysis of training opportunities in registry

After completion of the initial data entry phase the registry now has details of sixty six training events, ranging from 2008 to upcoming events in 2011. The work package is aware that this list is not comprehensive and therefore definitive trends and gaps in the digital curation training landscape cannot be easily drawn from the data available. However, HATII has worked through the entries and noted some initial observations that may be useful to feed into the development of the evaluation framework and DigCurV curriculum. Data under the headings of duration, country, language and audience were counted to identify the most popular for each, and the title and learning objectives of each course were studied in order to compile a list of topics covered and to identify any trends with regards to the types of courses being delivered.

Country and Language

The country with the highest number of entries in the registry is the United Kingdom with twenty six, indicating that training in digital curation is well established in this country. Other countries in Western Europe, namely Germany, France, Italy and the Netherlands also have a good number of entries, and several other European countries are represented with either one or two events each: Czech Republic, Spain, Sweden, Estonia, Lithuania, Belgium and Austria. Despite the larger countries of Western Europe dominating the entries there is a good representation of countries throughout Europe as a whole, showing there is an awareness of and need for training on digital curation throughout the region.

The majority of courses run outside the UK are delivered in that country's own language occasionally combined with some English. The few exceptions to this are courses run by European projects such as Planets and DigitalPreservationEurope, which are usually in English. These findings tend to suggest that training remains focused at a regional or national level, with the occasional event from a larger project targeting a more Europe-wide audience.

Duration and subject matter

The duration of courses varies from under half a day to several months. Courses spread across a number of months tend to focus on digital curation within a specific subject context or offer an academic qualification at the end, such as a Masters degree. Training events that last between one and two weeks are almost always more general courses on the principles of digital curation or preservation, whilst courses lasting between half and two days fall into two categories; either a brief overview of the topic of digital curation, or more often training on a specific issue or aspect of the topic.

With regards to subject matter, entries can be broadly categorised into three areas:

- Courses offering an introduction/training on the principles of digital curation and preservation
- Courses offering training on specific methods/tools/services developed by a certain project
- Courses delivering training on a particular aspect of digital curation or digitisation.

Below is a more detailed list of topics identified as covered by courses in the registry:

- Access and reuse
- Audio/media
- Audit and certification
- Digital archives
- Digitisation
- Electronic records management
- File formats
- Legal - IPR/Licensing/Copyright

- Metadata
- OAIS
- Planning for digital collections
- Policy
- Preservation approaches – migration, emulation
- Preservation planning
- Repositories/management systems
- Research data management
- Security
- Standards
- Tools of a project/organisation
- Web archiving

A comprehensive variety of topics seem to be covered by the courses analysed. Earlier entries are predominantly courses on the principles of digital preservation, with themes such as OAIS, metadata and preservation planning focused on repeatedly. As the entries move on to more recent courses however a greater number of shorter courses on specific aspects, such as IPR and copyright, or on managing specific types of digital material, such as media and audio collections, begin to emerge. Though it is difficult to draw definite conclusions from the number of entries available, we might surmise that as more people are educated in and become familiar with the overall principles of digital preservation and curation, there is a growing need for courses that cover particular aspects or types of digital curation in more detail.

Audience

Training for the Practical audience type has proved the most common, with fifty three courses being recorded as aimed at this group. The Managerial group are listed for twenty one courses, and Executive for twelve. Shorter courses on a specific topic (such as many of those listed for 2011) tend to be targeted towards a practical audience, probably as these are usually the group with a need for in-depth knowledge on certain actions or procedures. Longer non-academic courses are generally aimed at all audience levels, in keeping with their aim to teach the broader principles. Courses that specifically target the Executive group are short events focused around issues such as policy.

Overall findings to be fed into evaluation framework and subsequent curriculum design

- Training in native languages remains dominant – the curriculum should take into account the desire to deliver courses in the language of the country where the event takes place
- The duration of courses is highly dependent on the subject, audience level and whether there is any official accreditation as a result, suggesting a mixture of course lengths tailored to these elements will be necessary
- Courses on the principles of digital curation remain popular, but there is also an increasing number of shorter specialist courses, indicating a need for the principles to be placed in context or expanded for a practical audience
- Fewer courses are targeted specifically at the Managerial and Executive audience. This could be due to less need or demand from these groups, but it will be necessary to carefully consider the training needs of these groups and ensure they are equally well represented in the curriculum

6. Future use of the registry

DigCurV have already promoted the registry through the project's Twitter and Facebook pages, and will provide information in subsequent newsletters encouraging individuals to continue adding relevant entries. It is hoped that over time the registry can become a definitive list of training opportunities for the digital curation community, to which managers, practitioners and others refer. In order to achieve this it will be important for the project to build relationships with cultural institutions and competence centres in digital curation, and to encourage them to consult and populate the registry. The project's planned dissemination activities and partners' strong networking capabilities provide the mechanisms for ensuring this.

7. References

DigCurV Training opportunities registry: <http://www.digcur-education.org/eng/Training-opportunities>.

DPOE pyramid <http://www.digitalpreservation.gov/education/index.html>

Karvelyte, V., Klingaite N., and Kupriene, J., 'Interim report on the baseline survey of training opportunities, DigCurV 2011.